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Effect of primer and sealant in refill friction stir spot welded joints on strength and fatigue behaviour of aluminium alloys

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ABSTRACT

The refill friction stir spot welding (RFSSW) is one of the promising friction stir welding (FSW) methods consisting in the joint creation by plunging and retracting the rotating tool into the overlapped sheets without an exit hole after welding.

This work aims to fulfil a knowledge gap related to use of aluminium semi-products in a final configuration state (including anodizing, primer and sealant application) for RFSSW process by means of the lap-shear and cross-tension mechanical test, fatigue performance, metallographic and fractographic analyses, and digital image correlation (DIC) technique. Sheet semi-products of thicknesses from 2 to 3 mm made of AA7050-T7451 and AA2024-T3 aluminium alloys in bare and/or anodised condition were used for the lap-joint specimens manufacturing and five various material joint combinations were analysed.

The effect on static strength for the joint configurations with primer and sealant was studied and compared with the bare materials' RFSSW joints. Fatigue tests showed that the primed configurations exhibited a higher scatter of the results and a different slope of fatigue curve with a higher fatigue limit value as compared with the bare material's joints exhibiting a higher ultimate static strength.

1. Introduction

Development of friction stir welding (FSW) and friction stir spot welding (FSSW) has been progressing rapidly over the last few years and certain applications have been identified as beneficial for the aerospace industry [1]. In contrast to conventional welding techniques where the joined components are melted to create the joint, FSW and FSSW mechanically intermixes the materials at lower temperatures. The heat affected zone and overall property degradation for FSW is therefore less than for many other welding techniques and is more comparable to fastener joining techniques in terms of strength and fatigue resistance [2,3].

Even the riveted structure is based on the well-established design standards and has the required reliability, welded joints can be performed at a higher rate than traditional fastener joints as it involves fewer process steps (no need for drilling, disassembly, de-burring, re-assembly and insertion/pulling of fasteners). Welding also allows for higher structural integration, possibly resulting in weight savings in the new design of profiles aimed for FSW and cost reduction as well as reduced environmental impact. Joining using rivets is more time consuming than using welding approaches enabling improved

aerodynamics and light-weighting which subsequently will improve fuel efficiency and global competitiveness of the industry [4].

The refill friction stir spot welding (RFSSW) is one of the promising FSW methods consisting in the joint creation by plunging and retracting the rotating tool into the overlapped sheets. Traditional friction stir spot welding leaves an exit hole upon retraction after welding resulting in poor joint properties. The RFSSW provides a fully consolidated surface.

RFSSW has been patented by Schilling and dos Santos [5] and numerous researchers studied and optimised welding process parameters [6,7,8], mechanical properties [9,10,11,12], and microstructures [13,14] of various materials.

The RFSSW simply consists in the following five continuous basic stages: (1) after clamping of two sheets to be welded by a ring part (tight holding of the pieces and avoiding a plasticized material to escape during the process) and initial frictional preheating by rotating of tool components at the sheet surface contact; (2) plunging of the shoulder/sleeve or probe to a pre-defined depth; (3) reinjection/refilling the weld region with the displaced material by reversing of the shoulder and probe movement; (4) alignment of the probe and the shoulder to establish the final flush surface; and (5) extraction of the tool from the material and unclamping the welded sheets. More detailed description

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Fig. 1. The RFSSW sequence: First the clamping ring, sleeve/shoulder and probe are level and pressed against the material surface (A). The rotating sleeve is plunged into the material and plasticised material is pushed up into the volume create by the probe (B). Then the movement of the probe and sleeve is reversed, and the probe material is pushed down (C). Finally, the tool is retracted, leaving a flush weld surface (D).

Table 1
Chemical composition of the experimental materials (in wt.%).

Aluminium alloy	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Cr	Zn	Ti	Zr	Others		Al
										Single	Total	
AA2024	0.5	0.5	3.8–4.9	0.3–0.9	1.2–1.8	0.1	0.25	0.15	–	0.05	0.15	bal.
T3												
AA7050	0.12	0.15	2.0–2.6	0.1	1.9–2.6	0.04	5.7–6.7	0.06	0.08–0.15	0.05	0.15	bal.
T7451												

Table 2
Mechanical properties of the experimental materials (SD – standard deviation).

Aluminium alloy	Yield stress (MPa)		Tensile strength (MPa)		Elongation (%)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
	Alclad AA2024-T3	301	1.5	442	0.8	21.3
AA7050-T7451	480	0.9	534	1.4	11.7	0.4

of the RFSSW process could be fined in [7]. Example of the RFSSW process sequence is schematically shown in Fig. 1.

Although many organisations recognised these advantages and benefits, further research is required to implement this technology into large-scale production and increase the current technology readiness level. The overall aim of the work is to fill the knowledge gap related to use of aluminium semi-products in a final configuration state including anodizing, primer, and sealant application. Many of the FSW process parameters have a detrimental effect on a weld quality [15,16] but there is still a lack of studies on industrial fluids effect on FSW processing quality. Especially in terms of fatigue, where only “pure” RFSSW has been studied [17,18,19], and very few papers have been published focusing on the application of RFSSW process to parts with protective layers or coatings used in the aerospace industry. Already in 2007, it was

Table 3
RFSSW coupon trial conditions.

Coupon combination	Top sheet		Bottom sheet		Sealant applied
	material & thickness	interface condition	material & thickness	interface condition	
72	AA7050/2 mm	Bare	AA2024/2.85 mm	Bare	No
72APS	AA7050/2 mm	Anodised & primer	AA2024/2.85 mm	Bare	Yes
77	AA7050/2 mm	Bare	AA7050/2 mm	Bare	No
77APS	AA7050/2 mm	Anodised & primer	AA7050/2 mm	Anodised & primer	Yes
22	AA2024/2 mm	Bare	AA2024/2 mm	Bare	No
72ALOD	AA7050/2 mm	Anodised & Alodine	AA2024/2.85 mm	Anodised & Alodine	Yes
77ALOD	AA7050/2 mm	Anodised & Alodine	AA7050/2 mm	Anodised & Alodine	Yes

demonstrated that FSW could be successfully applied through AA7075 sheets with a sealant at the faying surface with an improved corrosion behaviour after an exposure to a salt spray corrosive environment [20]. In the same year, Christner patented a specific procedure for the

Fig. 2. Welding tool.

application of an uncured polymer surface sealant before FSW process in USA [21]. Effect of an interfacial sealant presence on the RFSSW properties has been recently studied on AA7075 [12] and dissimilar AA7075/AA2024 [6,22] lap-joints and it was showed that the RFSSW process is complex with a nuisance effect of the sealant if the welding parameters are chosen inappropriately. However, the fatigue strength has been improved by application of faying surface sealant [6,22].

This paper is focused on assessment of the primer application effect on the mechanical (static and fatigue) properties of RFSSW joints made from AA7050-T7451 and AA2024-T3 sheets representing a frame and skin, respectively, for a specific design of Cargo door demonstrator within OASIS European project. The overall objective of the project is to demonstrate the ability and cost-effectiveness of manufacturing aluminium aircraft structures using the latest developments in friction

Fig. 3. Drawing of the RFSSW lap-shear (a) and cross-tension test specimen (b); in mm.

Fig. 4. Spot weld tensile lap-shear (left) and cross-tension (right) test set-up.

Table 4
Summary of the static lap-shear and cross-tension test results.

Coupon combination	Lap shear strength (kN)				Cross-tension strength (kN)			
	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max
77	10.06	0.41	9.80	10.53	4.46	0.19	4.28	4.65
22	8.21	0.16	8.06	8.38	3.19	0.09	3.10	3.27
72	8.51	0.60	7.99	9.17	4.13	0.57	3.51	4.64
77APS	3.46	0.68	2.60	4.26	1.76	0.13	1.66	1.91
72APS	6.38	0.86	5.56	7.27	1.57	0.32	1.31	1.93
77ALOD	9.07	0.48	8.58	9.53	2.32	1.20	1.46	3.69
72ALOD	8.08	0.48	7.78	8.63	2.93	0.26	2.71	3.21

Fig. 5. Summary of the static lap-shear and cross-tension test results.

Fig. 6. Typical shear interfacial failure modes of the lap-shear test coupons.

Fig. 7. Typical failure modes of the cross-tension test coupons – various modes for primed (interfacial failure) and primer-free (top sheet nugget pull-out failure mode) configurations.

Fig. 8. DIC - different strain distribution during the lap-shear test for the bare (left) and primed (right) configurations – view from the welding top side.

Fig. 9. Fatigue lap-joint test results – comparison of bare configurations; R = 0.1, 15 Hz.

stir welding (FSW) and laser beam welding (LBW). The experimental procedure, sample design and manufacturing, metallographic examinations, and other work associated with the primer effect evaluation are presented in this paper. Various coupon configurations including bare, primed and primer-free materials were studied.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Commercial aluminium alloys, AA7050-T7451 and Alclad 2024-T3 of thickness of 2 mm and 2.8 mm, respectively, were used as the input

materials for the refill friction stir spot welding RFSSW experiments. The chemical composition of the sheet materials is listed in Table 1.

The mechanical properties of the experimental materials assessed using the tensile test according to EN ISO 6892-1 (2020) standard at room temperature are summarized in Table 2.

No post-welding heat treatment has been performed. For configurations with a faying surface sealant, a manganese dioxide-based polysulphide polymer sealant widely used in the aerospace industry has been applied. Totally, seven coupon configurations (3 baseline including the dissimilar spot weld and always 2 with and without the primer application) were studied:

- AA7050-AA7050 (no interface), designated as batch 77,
- AA2024-AA2024 (no interface), designated as batch 22,
- dissimilar spot weld AA7050-AA2024 (no interface), batch 72,
- AA7050 (anodised + primed) – AA7050 (anodised + primed) + sealant, batch 77APS,
- AA7050 (anodised + primed) – AA2024 + sealant, batch 72APS,
- AA7050 (anodised + Alodine) – AA7050 (anodised + Alodine) + sealant, batch 77ALOD,
- AA7050 (anodised + Alodine) – AA2024 (anodised + Alodine) + sealant, batch 72ALOD.

In case of the primer-free configurations, the area where welding occurred was covered by a masking tape during the primer application, so a primer-free region was available for the welding. And, to add extra corrosion protection, both weld interface surfaces of the AA2024-T3 and AA7050-T7451 parts have been anodised and Alodine (chromate conversion) corrosion protective coating has been applied before welding. All RFSSW coupon combination materials and interfaces are clearly summarized in Table 3.

Fig. 10. Fatigue lap-joint test results – primer effect comparison of bare, with primer/sealant and no-primer/sealant/external corrosion protection for 7050–7050 (left) and 7050–2024 (right) configurations; $R = 0.1$, 15 Hz.

Fig. 11. Microstructure overview (c) and detailed micrographs of the RFSSW joint (AA7050 – AA7050, bare) cross-section: ((a) thermo-mechanically affected zones (TMAZ) in the upper part of the weld, (b) TMAZ in the bottom part of the weld, (d) unbonded and partially bonded region, (e) SZ/TMAZ: in the bottom part of the weld microstructure.

2.2. Coupon welding

The RFSSW coupons were produced using the KHI Robotic FSSW system with 6-axis articulating arm (C-Frame design) force range from 1.5 to 15 kN, maximum revolutions speed of 2160 rpm, and maximum pressure shaft stroke of 180 mm. The welding tool (see Fig. 2) was fabricated from a metal matrix composite material (WC particles/Co binder) with a diamond like Carbon coating. The welding process

parameters were a rotational speed of 1200 rpm and a plunge depth of 2.2 mm at force of 13.5 kN using a 16 mm diameter clamping ring, 7 mm diameter shoulder, and 4 mm diameter probe. The KHI system uses a shoulder-first sequences, as shown in Fig. 1. The sleeve plunges at a constant speed and total weld procedure takes 7 s, consisting of 2 s sleeve plunge, 3 s dwell time, and 2 s of the sleeve retraction.

Two types of the RFSSW test coupons have been manufactured – parallelly and perpendicularly overlapped sheets for the lap-shear and

Fig. 12. Microstructure overview (c) and detailed micrographs of the RFSSW joint (AA7050 – AA7050, APS) cross-section: (a) thermo-mechanically affected zones (TMAZ), (b) stir zone (SZ), (d) SZ in the upper centre of the weld, (e) SZ – TMAZ interface in the bottom part of the weld heat affected zone (HAZ) microstructure.

cross-tension tests, respectively, see schemes in Fig. 3. All test coupons have been manufactured and welded at TWI.

2.3. Test procedures

The static and fatigue lap-shear tests were carried out with shims in the gripping area according to the EN ISO 14273 [23] standard without a guiding fixture by means of Sinus (100 kN load cell) testing machine using hydraulic wedge grips (Fig. 4 left). The static tests were done under displacement control at the test rate of 0.25 mm/min. The fatigue tests were done under load control using a harmonic loading (sinusoidal shape of the loading cycle) with a constant load amplitude. Cyclic

loading of the specimens was performed at one level of stress ratio $R = 0.1$ (tension–tension mode) and at nominal test frequency of 15 Hz. Fatigue curve was generated by performing series of experiments at appropriate maximum load levels, such that the desired range from 10^3 to $5 \cdot 10^6$ cycles was achieved. The loading had been applied until a specimen's failure or until 4 million cycles were reached and the test terminated without a failure (run-out).

The static cross-tension tests were carried out according to the EN ISO 14272 [24] standard by means of Instron 55R1185 (10 kN load cell) testing machine using a special fixture (Fig. 4 right). The tests were done under displacement control at the test rate of 2 mm/min. Three specimens from each configuration have been tested in case of the static

Fig. 13. Microstructure overview (c) and detailed micrographs of the RFSSW joint (AA7050 – AA7050, ALODINE) cross-section: (a) thermo-mechanically affected zones (TMAZ) – stir zone (SZ) interface, (b) partial bonding interface in the TMAZ, (d) bonding ligament in SZ, (e) SZ in the bottom part of the weld.

testing. In case of fatigue tests, at least 8 tests have been performed to get Wöhler curve for each test batch.

Photogrammetric Dantec Q-400 system, enabling digital image correlation (DIC) analysis, was used to monitor the deformation state during loading. The specimen's middle region was monitored to obtain full-field strain distribution map. The surface of the specimen was sprayed by a chalk coating and black spray to get a sufficiently random texture. The proper illumination was provided by a 250 W halogen lamp with heat-reflecting filters.

Metallographic samples have been prepared using standard grinding and polishing methods. The final polishing was performed using the MasterPrep Alumina Polishing Suspension (0.05 μm). Microstructure of the samples was revealed by electrolytic Barker's anodising method with subsequent optical microstructural contrasting in polarized light. The magnifications up to 1000× were used within the metallographic analyses.

Fractographic analyses of the fracture surface after the fatigue testing were performed by means of TESCAN VEGA 3SBU Scanning

Electron Microscope (SEM) set to the secondary electrons (SE) or back-scattered electrons (BSE) imaging modes. The high vacuum mode with a voltage value of 20 kV was used for the evaluation. Chemical composition determination was performed using the energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) microanalyser INCA x-act SDD (Oxford instruments). The measurements and mapping analyses were performed by means of the AZtec software. All tests and analyses have been performed at the Czech Aerospace Research Centre.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Static strength

The static lap-shear and cross-tension test results are tabularly and graphically summarized in Table 4 and Fig. 5, respectively. RFSSW configurations with primer and sealant showed an evident decrease in strength as compared with the bare condition (by 65 % and 25 % in case of the 7050–7050 and dissimilar 7050–2024 configurations,

Fig. 14. Fracture surface micrographs of the of primed 7050–7050 RFSSW joint after fatigue lap-shear test (load level of 3.3 kN; fatigue life of 7 000 cycles) – (a) top and (b) bottom view on the specimen failure; overview micrographs in SE (c) and BSE (d) modes; and details of quasi-statically (e) and cyclically loaded (f) failure areas.

respectively). If the configurations with primer/sealant and no-primer/sealant are compared, there is a significant improvement of the mechanical properties in case of primer-free configuration. There was a decrease by only 10 % and 5 % in case of the 7050–7050 and dissimilar 7050–2024 configurations, respectively, when compared to the bare configurations. The cross-tension test results are in a good agreement with the lap-shear test ones. The most significant difference in the lap-shear (LS) and cross-tension (CT) strength values (the lowest CT/LS

ratio) can be observed in the primed AA7050-AA2024 and primer-free AA7050-AA7050 configurations (25 %), while the usual value of this ratio is 40–45 % [13,25]. The low CT/LS ratio values are given by a relatively high lap-shear strength values as compared to the counterparts of the same configuration (AA7050-AA7050 with primer and primer-free AA7050-AA2024), while the same cross-tension test results were observed for the corresponding configurations.

For a general comparison, the lap-shear test results were compared

Fig. 15. Fracture surface micrographs of the of primer-free/sealant 7050–7050 RFSSW joint after fatigue lap-shear test (load level of 3.3 kN; fatigue life of 59 000 cycles) – (a) top and (b) bottom view on the specimen failure; overview micrographs in SE (c) and BSE (d) modes; and details of cyclically (e) and quasi-statically loaded (f) failure areas.

with the minimum shear load value of 4.7 kN required for the spot weld according to AWS D17.2 [26] and shear strength of the solid Al rivet (2024-T4) of 255 MPa according to NASM 20426 [27]. The shear load values, that are higher by two thirds and one half than the typical riveted joint, are evident from this comparison for the primer-free AA7050 and dissimilar AA7050-AA2024 joints, respectively.

The lap-shear test coupons exclusively exhibited shear interfacial failure mode for all configurations, as shown in Fig. 6. The failure usually occurs along an interface between the top and bottom sheets because of an insufficient plunge depth induces a smaller and weaker weld nugget or when the parent material thicknesses are relatively larger than the spot weld diameter [7].

The cross-tension test coupons' failure mode differed for the primed

and primer-free configurations, see Fig. 7. Whilst the primed configurations exhibited the interfacial failure, the top sheet nugget pull-out failure was observed on the primer-free configurations when the weld nugget is pulled out of the top sheet in the thermo-mechanically affected zone (TMAZ). Only in case of the primer-free 7050–7050 coupons with the sealant, one test specimen (from three available) exhibited the interfacial failure resulting in the lowest strength value of 1.5 kN (the maximum value measured was 3.7 kN) explaining a large scatter of almost 50 %, see Table 4.

3.2. Strain analysis

Different lap-shear test loading behaviour of the bare and primed

Fig. 16. EDX maps of chemical elements distribution on the fracture surface of primed 7050–7050 RFSSW joint (centre area) after fatigue lap-shear test.

configurations resulting in dissimilar failure modes was confirmed also by the digital image correlation (DIC) measurements. Engineering tangential strain (in loading direction) maps of all bare and primed configurations showing a various strain distribution just before a final failure of the lap-shear test specimens are presented in Fig. 8. The primed configuration exhibited a round, highly localized strain distribution concentrated in the nugget stir zone of the weld in contrast to bare weld where a typical “butterfly” type of the strain distribution could be observed. This difference is caused by a rotation of weld nugget given by asymmetric nature of the loading of the refill spot weld in terms of a partial penetration of the welding tool into the bottom sheet [7,9,14]. In case of the primed/sealant configurations, this phenomenon is suppressed by a “sticking” effect of the sealant applied around the

welded area (see Fig. 6).

The primed RFSSW specimens exhibited tensile and compressive strains at an interface of the thermo-mechanically affected (TMAZ) and heat affected (HAZ) zones’ circumference halves above and below the weld, respectively, regarding the loading direction shown in Fig. 8. In case of the primed 7050–7050 specimen, there is evident partial debonding of welded sheets in the final stages of the test (see Fig. 8 bottom-right) when symmetric positive strain wings could be observed under an angle of 45° below the welded area.

This phenomenon is typical for the unguided lap-shear testing of the bare configurations’ specimens, where the rotation of the weld nugget occurred resulting in presence of a combination of shear and pull-out (normal direction to sheet surface) forces [7,13,14]. The negative

Fig. 17. EDX maps of chemical elements distribution on the fracture surface of primer-free/sealant 7050–7050 RFSSW joint (centre area) after fatigue lap-shear test.

strain zones shifted towards the weld nugget centre that resulted in limiting of the positive strain zone size down to only one third of the weld nugget circumference half (see Fig. 8 left).

3.3. Fatigue behaviour

Fatigue behaviour of the bare materials' RFSSW configurations under lap-joint test cycling is compared in Fig. 9. There is no substantial variation in fatigue curve shape, but a superior fatigue behaviour could be observed for the 7050–2024 configuration. The graphical interpretation of the primer application effect on fatigue test results is shown in Fig. 10. The primed configurations exhibit a higher scatter of the results and a different slope of the fatigue curve as compared to other weld configurations.

From a comparison of the sealed configurations with primer and without-primer, it is evident that there is fatigue life improvement in case of no-primer batches despite the lower fatigue limit levels. The worse fatigue behaviour of the bare configurations is caused by the unguided character of the loading during the lap-shear test, see paragraphs above. This corresponds well with the results obtained in works [6,22]. A higher variability and downgrade of the fatigue lives observed in case of the primed 7050–7050 configuration could be explained using microscopic analyses results described in the following paragraph.

3.4. Microstructure characterization

Effect of primer and sealant application in RFSSW joints on microstructure is demonstrated using the 7050–7050 weld configuration. Microstructure overview and detailed micrographs of the bare, primed,

and primer-free configurations of 7050–7050 RFSSW joints are shown in Fig. 11 to Fig. 13, respectively. Typical FSW microstructure, containing nugget stir zone (SZ), thermo-mechanically affected zones (TMAZ), and heat affected zone (HAZ) transitioning smoothly into base material (BM) area, could be observed in all weld configurations. It is evident that the sealant interlayer is stirred well with the base material. The remaining sealant microlayers are visible accumulated predominantly in the central area of the SZ. This agrees well with previously published results [12], only an excessive amount of the sealant highly concentrated at SZ and TMAZ corner area interface has not been observed in the present microstructure of the primer-free configuration (see Fig. 13). On the other hand, this was the case for the samples with the primary coating (Fig. 12), where comparable amount of the primer residues has been detected as compared to the results published in [12].

The primed and primer-free welds differ in shape of stirred zone, grain size distribution, and, especially, in a bonding ligament thickness between SZ and TMAZ zones when the primed configuration exhibits an irregular and partially bonded interface resulting in a higher strain concentration in that weakened area during mechanical testing (Fig. 8) that is in good coincidence with observations in [6,12]. Moreover, there is an insufficient depth of the weld nugget in case of the primed 7050–7050 joint (Fig. 12) when the interface between the SZ and TMAZ lies at the connection surfaces of two welded sheets. This could be the reason of the higher variability of the fatigue lives and the worst fatigue behaviour observed in case of the primed 7050–7050 configuration, especially at higher loading levels (Fig. 10 left). This poor weld quality was not observed in any other RFSSW configuration.

3.5. Fractographic analysis

Fracture surfaces of the primed and primer-free 7050–7050 RFSSW joints with sealant after the fatigue test at the maximum load level of 3.3 kN (corresponding to fatigue life of 7 and 59 thousand cycles, respectively) are for a comparison presented in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15, respectively. A nugget debonding failure mode could be observed in both configurations that is typical for lap-shear test loading [12,13,18]. The fracture surface micrographs confirmed the microscopic observations (Fig. 12) of the irregular and partially bonded interface between SZ and TMAZ zones in the primed weld (primer residues could be observed in central area of the fracture surface in Fig. 16). This led to a strain concentration resulting in substantially shorter fatigue life (8-times) for the primed configurations. The primer-free fracture surface centre contained sealant particles on base of sulphur, molybdenum, and silicon elements (see Fig. 17).

A multi-site failure initiation at the SZ and TMAZ circumferential interface, where a partial bonding was present, could be observed on the primed 7050–7050 configuration fracture surface. In case of the primer-free/sealant 7050–7050 configuration, the fracture surface smoother and clear and the major initiation site (shown by the white arrow in Fig. 15c) occurred at the transverse direction (to the loading direction) interface between the SZ and TMAZ along the bonding ligaments (see Fig. 13), similar to the fracture surface analysed in [22]. However, a multi-site failure initiation at the tensile circumferential nugget interface could be observed also on the primer-free test specimen fracture surface.

4. Conclusion

This study investigated the static and fatigue properties of the refill friction stir spot welded (RFSSW) aluminium semi-products in a final configuration state (including anodizing, primer, and sealant application). The testing on various AA7050 and AA2024 material configurations provided the following results:

- RFSSW configurations with primer and sealant showed an evident decrease in strength as compared with the bare condition. If the configurations with primer/sealant and no-primer/sealant are compared, there is a significant improvement of the mechanical properties in case of primer-free configuration.
- The primed configurations exhibit a higher scatter of the results. The primer-free welds exhibited an improved fatigue behaviour with a higher slope of the fatigue curve.
- The primed configurations exhibited a round, highly localized strain distribution concentrated in the nugget stir zone of the weld caused by an irregular and partially bonded interface between stirred and thermo-mechanically affected zones in the primed welds leading to a substantially shorter fatigue life for the primed configurations.
- Negative effect of the primer during welding could be solved by covering using a masking tape during the primer application, so a primer-free region was available for the welding. Application of an extra corrosion protection (Alodine chromate conversion coating) before welding had not affect the RFSSW properties significantly.

Generally, the experimental works conducted demonstrated that optimised application of corrosion inhibitors before the RFSSW process (offering opportunities to not only reduce a product weight, but also manufacturing time and costs) resulted in only 5–10 % reduction in lap-shear strength and an improved fatigue behaviour (3 to 5-times longer fatigue lives) as compared with the bare configurations.

The effect of studied industrial fluids on FSW processing quality and properties needs to be verified also from the corrosion resistance point of view and this will be the subject of future work.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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